

Leveraging a Neural-Symbolic Representation of Biomedical Knowledge to Improve Pediatric Subphenotyping

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

PILOT STUDY: These results are preliminary and will be updated prior to publication

The Supplemental Material includes documentation on the procedures used to obtain and de-identify the pediatric EHR data analyzed in this project. These procedures were approved as non-human subjects research by Colorado Multiple Internal Review Board (15-0445).

The Supplemental Material also contains additional figures from the Medicine to Mechanism pilot study described in [Section 6.1.1](#). The appendix contains two tables: (i) full classification results and (ii) clinical data that was obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus for the study titled “The Genomic Architecture of Sickle Cell Disease in Children from West Africa” ([GSE35007](#)).

Quinlan J, Idaghdour Y, Goulet JP, Gbeha E, de Malliard T, Bruat V, Grenier JC, Gomez S, Sanni A, Rahimy MC, Awadalla P. Genomic architecture of sickle cell disease in West African children. *Frontiers in Genetics*. 2014;5:26.
[PMID: 24592274](#)

The data in the table features the original clinical data provided by the study, but mapped to the Human Disease (DOID) and Human Phenotype (HP) ontologies. The HP concepts were mapped to laboratory measurement results using a standard pediatric reference range from the Mayo Clinic¹. Normal values were indicated as NOT the HP immediate HP ancestor concept of the HP concepts mapped for high and low results. For example, the mapping results for mean corpuscular volume are shown below:

- Within Reference Range: Normal (NOT [HP:0025065](#))
- Below Reference Range: Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume ([HP:0025066](#))
- Above Reference Range: Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume ([HP:0005518](#))

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¹Mayo Clinic Pediatric Reference Range: [30a2131-complete-blood-count-normal-pediatric-values.pdf](#)

De-Identified OMOP CDM Repository - Data Processing Procedures

The proposed project aims to facilitate recurring transfer of data from the currently existing Children's Hospital of Colorado (CHCO) Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) limited data repository into a completely de-identified OMOP CDM data repository. Specific steps taken during the transfer to data from the CHCO OMOP CDM limited data repository into the de-identified OMOP CDM data repository include:

Identifier Generation

Masked patient identifiers will have already been assigned to each record as part of the initial transfer of data into the CHCO OMOP CDM limited data repository. When data is transferred into the OMOP CDM de-identified data set a completely new set of identifiers will be created. Once this transformation is complete, identifier mapping tables will be destroyed.

Date Shifting

Obfuscation will be used to de-identify dates each time data is transferred from the CHCO OMOP CDM limited data repository to the OMOP CDM de-identified data repository. This obfuscation process involves adding a random number of days to all dates associated with a patient; each patient's dates are shifted by a different random number of days. A uniform random distribution will be used to generate a random number of days to shift dates between -60 to +60 days (a 120 day interval). Once the mapping information used to shift the dates is destroyed the process cannot be reversed. Since date obfuscation may potentially impact aggregate numbers (i.e., can cause patients to shift into or out of time intervals), analyses and interpretation of findings will be known to be approximate, which adds an additional layer of patient privacy protection.

Zip Code Alteration

As specified in HIPAA Safe Harbor rules for de-identification, only the first three digits of each zip code will be included. Removing the location data for zip codes containing less than 25 individuals will help to ensure that individuals from less populated zip codes cannot be identified.

Supplemental Table 1. Representation Classification Performance by Clinical Domain.

STANDARD OMOP CLINICAL TERMINOLOGIES													
Domain	Parameter Setting	Logistic Regression				Support Vector Machine				Bernoulli Naïve Bayes			
		Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁
DX	BoW+TF-IDF	0.989	0.990	0.989	0.989	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.870	0.890	0.870	0.871
	DM:100:5	0.736	0.752	0.736	0.738	0.738	0.758	0.738	0.740	0.604	0.640	0.604	0.602
	DM:100:10	0.702	0.721	0.702	0.704	0.710	0.733	0.710	0.712	0.538	0.597	0.538	0.532
	DM:100:15	0.670	0.689	0.670	0.671	0.678	0.700	0.678	0.678	0.512	0.572	0.512	0.503
	DM:100:20	0.674	0.689	0.674	0.671	0.671	0.688	0.671	0.668	0.516	0.598	0.516	0.509
	DM:150:5	0.739	0.754	0.739	0.740	0.753	0.775	0.753	0.755	0.614	0.656	0.614	0.611
	DM:150:10	0.702	0.722	0.702	0.704	0.708	0.733	0.708	0.711	0.534	0.600	0.534	0.525
	DM:150:15	0.675	0.693	0.675	0.675	0.689	0.711	0.689	0.690	0.523	0.593	0.523	0.520
	DM:150:20	0.657	0.675	0.657	0.656	0.667	0.687	0.667	0.665	0.502	0.596	0.502	0.499
	DM:200:5	0.735	0.750	0.735	0.736	0.745	0.765	0.745	0.747	0.591	0.638	0.591	0.585
	DM:200:10	0.709	0.729	0.709	0.711	0.725	0.749	0.725	0.728	0.558	0.613	0.558	0.551
	DM:200:15	0.689	0.708	0.689	0.690	0.704	0.726	0.704	0.704	0.520	0.591	0.520	0.513
	DM:200:20	0.662	0.682	0.662	0.662	0.675	0.696	0.675	0.675	0.508	0.593	0.508	0.500
	DBOW:100:5	0.805	0.811	0.805	0.805	0.810	0.816	0.810	0.810	0.720	0.726	0.720	0.718
	DBOW:100:10	0.804	0.811	0.804	0.804	0.811	0.818	0.811	0.812	0.700	0.708	0.700	0.698
	DBOW:100:15	0.805	0.812	0.805	0.805	0.814	0.821	0.814	0.814	0.721	0.727	0.721	0.721
	DBOW:100:20	0.797	0.806	0.797	0.797	0.805	0.813	0.805	0.806	0.711	0.719	0.711	0.709
	DBOW:150:5	0.810	0.817	0.810	0.810	0.819	0.826	0.819	0.819	0.726	0.733	0.726	0.726
	DBOW:150:10	0.801	0.808	0.801	0.801	0.814	0.821	0.814	0.814	0.732	0.737	0.732	0.730
	DBOW:150:15	0.800	0.807	0.800	0.801	0.813	0.819	0.813	0.813	0.722	0.728	0.722	0.720
DBOW:150:20	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.809	0.817	0.824	0.817	0.817	0.729	0.734	0.729	0.728	
DBOW:200:5	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.808	0.819	0.827	0.819	0.820	0.731	0.737	0.731	0.729	
DBOW:200:10	0.810	0.817	0.810	0.810	0.820	0.826	0.820	0.820	0.737	0.745	0.737	0.736	
DBOW:200:15	0.809	0.816	0.809	0.809	0.819	0.826	0.819	0.819	0.735	0.742	0.735	0.736	
DBOW:200:20	0.799	0.807	0.799	0.800	0.810	0.818	0.810	0.810	0.732	0.738	0.732	0.731	
RX	BoW+TF-IDF	0.931	0.932	0.931	0.931	0.954	0.954	0.954	0.954	0.813	0.852	0.813	0.817
	DM:100:5	0.760	0.770	0.760	0.761	0.766	0.778	0.766	0.767	0.601	0.633	0.601	0.599
	DM:100:10	0.723	0.743	0.723	0.725	0.728	0.750	0.728	0.730	0.537	0.607	0.537	0.534
	DM:100:15	0.674	0.693	0.674	0.674	0.682	0.703	0.682	0.682	0.516	0.575	0.516	0.511
	DM:100:20	0.684	0.695	0.684	0.682	0.689	0.701	0.689	0.685	0.509	0.603	0.509	0.506
	DM:150:5	0.757	0.767	0.757	0.758	0.775	0.791	0.775	0.777	0.604	0.643	0.604	0.604
	DM:150:10	0.724	0.742	0.724	0.726	0.739	0.760	0.739	0.741	0.517	0.591	0.517	0.513
	DM:150:15	0.691	0.708	0.691	0.690	0.709	0.728	0.709	0.708	0.502	0.583	0.502	0.503
	DM:150:20	0.681	0.695	0.681	0.680	0.695	0.715	0.695	0.695	0.497	0.591	0.497	0.498
	DM:200:5	0.750	0.760	0.750	0.750	0.769	0.784	0.769	0.770	0.566	0.617	0.566	0.563
	DM:200:10	0.730	0.745	0.730	0.731	0.749	0.767	0.749	0.750	0.542	0.600	0.542	0.540
	DM:200:15	0.696	0.715	0.696	0.697	0.724	0.746	0.724	0.725	0.514	0.593	0.514	0.512
	DM:200:20	0.675	0.689	0.675	0.674	0.703	0.721	0.703	0.702	0.507	0.600	0.507	0.503
	DBOW:100:5	0.798	0.804	0.798	0.798	0.810	0.814	0.810	0.808	0.700	0.708	0.700	0.699
	DBOW:100:10	0.810	0.816	0.810	0.809	0.821	0.826	0.821	0.820	0.709	0.715	0.709	0.707
	DBOW:100:15	0.801	0.806	0.801	0.800	0.809	0.814	0.809	0.808	0.705	0.709	0.705	0.704
	DBOW:100:20	0.804	0.808	0.804	0.803	0.815	0.821	0.815	0.814	0.700	0.707	0.700	0.697
	DBOW:150:5	0.809	0.816	0.809	0.809	0.823	0.829	0.823	0.822	0.716	0.723	0.716	0.716
	DBOW:150:10	0.801	0.806	0.801	0.800	0.820	0.825	0.820	0.819	0.721	0.725	0.721	0.719
	DBOW:150:15	0.810	0.816	0.810	0.809	0.828	0.834	0.828	0.827	0.704	0.711	0.704	0.703
DBOW:150:20	0.808	0.812	0.808	0.807	0.818	0.823	0.818	0.817	0.709	0.712	0.709	0.708	
DBOW:200:5	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.807	0.820	0.827	0.820	0.819	0.723	0.729	0.723	0.722	
DBOW:200:10	0.808	0.812	0.808	0.807	0.823	0.828	0.823	0.821	0.730	0.739	0.730	0.730	
DBOW:200:15	0.807	0.812	0.807	0.806	0.820	0.826	0.820	0.819	0.723	0.729	0.723	0.724	
DBOW:200:20	0.804	0.810	0.804	0.804	0.819	0.825	0.819	0.818	0.726	0.732	0.726	0.725	

STANDARD OMOP CLINICAL TERMINOLOGIES

Domain	Parameter Setting	Logistic Regression				Support Vector Machine				Bernoulli Naïve Bayes			
		Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁
Lab	BoW+TF-IDF	0.833	0.835	0.833	0.833	0.850	0.855	0.850	0.850	0.573	0.674	0.573	0.561
	DM:100:5	0.742	0.757	0.742	0.744	0.745	0.766	0.745	0.747	0.606	0.641	0.606	0.604
	DM:100:10	0.703	0.722	0.703	0.704	0.706	0.729	0.706	0.708	0.545	0.605	0.545	0.540
	DM:100:15	0.674	0.696	0.674	0.676	0.678	0.701	0.678	0.679	0.520	0.579	0.520	0.511
	DM:100:20	0.665	0.682	0.665	0.663	0.667	0.684	0.667	0.663	0.513	0.600	0.513	0.507
	DM:150:5	0.737	0.753	0.737	0.738	0.748	0.769	0.748	0.750	0.619	0.656	0.619	0.616
	DM:150:10	0.699	0.719	0.699	0.701	0.707	0.731	0.707	0.709	0.533	0.599	0.533	0.524
	DM:150:15	0.675	0.695	0.675	0.675	0.684	0.704	0.684	0.683	0.515	0.589	0.515	0.510
	DM:150:20	0.665	0.681	0.665	0.663	0.678	0.698	0.678	0.677	0.510	0.601	0.510	0.506
	DM:200:5	0.729	0.744	0.729	0.731	0.745	0.766	0.745	0.746	0.584	0.630	0.584	0.577
	DM:200:10	0.708	0.728	0.708	0.710	0.724	0.748	0.724	0.726	0.554	0.609	0.554	0.548
	DM:200:15	0.682	0.701	0.682	0.682	0.695	0.717	0.695	0.695	0.519	0.594	0.519	0.513
	DM:200:20	0.664	0.682	0.664	0.663	0.680	0.700	0.680	0.679	0.512	0.599	0.512	0.505
	DBOW:100:5	0.806	0.812	0.806	0.806	0.816	0.821	0.816	0.816	0.724	0.730	0.724	0.723
	DBOW:100:10	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.809	0.817	0.823	0.817	0.817	0.705	0.712	0.705	0.703
	DBOW:100:15	0.807	0.813	0.807	0.807	0.817	0.824	0.817	0.818	0.721	0.726	0.721	0.720
	DBOW:100:20	0.806	0.814	0.806	0.807	0.818	0.825	0.818	0.818	0.715	0.722	0.715	0.713
	DBOW:150:5	0.806	0.812	0.806	0.806	0.817	0.824	0.817	0.817	0.726	0.732	0.726	0.725
	DBOW:150:10	0.805	0.812	0.805	0.805	0.816	0.823	0.816	0.816	0.735	0.740	0.735	0.733
	DBOW:150:15	0.801	0.808	0.801	0.802	0.813	0.820	0.813	0.813	0.724	0.730	0.724	0.723
DBOW:150:20	0.814	0.820	0.814	0.814	0.822	0.828	0.822	0.822	0.734	0.737	0.734	0.732	
DBOW:200:5	0.804	0.811	0.804	0.804	0.815	0.822	0.815	0.814	0.725	0.730	0.725	0.724	
DBOW:200:10	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.809	0.818	0.826	0.818	0.818	0.738	0.747	0.738	0.737	
DBOW:200:15	0.809	0.816	0.809	0.809	0.819	0.827	0.819	0.820	0.735	0.742	0.735	0.736	
DBOW:200:20	0.803	0.812	0.803	0.803	0.813	0.823	0.813	0.814	0.737	0.743	0.737	0.735	
All	BoW+TF-IDF	0.972	0.972	0.972	0.972	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.721	0.839	0.721	0.741
	DM:100:5	0.737	0.753	0.737	0.739	0.742	0.763	0.742	0.744	0.603	0.639	0.603	0.600
	DM:100:10	0.709	0.727	0.709	0.711	0.714	0.737	0.714	0.716	0.542	0.601	0.542	0.536
	DM:100:15	0.671	0.691	0.671	0.672	0.677	0.701	0.677	0.678	0.522	0.581	0.522	0.514
	DM:100:20	0.666	0.682	0.666	0.664	0.668	0.685	0.668	0.664	0.507	0.593	0.507	0.501
	DM:150:5	0.734	0.750	0.734	0.736	0.747	0.769	0.747	0.749	0.613	0.654	0.613	0.610
	DM:150:10	0.708	0.727	0.708	0.710	0.717	0.741	0.717	0.719	0.538	0.605	0.538	0.529
	DM:150:15	0.678	0.697	0.678	0.679	0.692	0.712	0.692	0.692	0.522	0.591	0.522	0.516
	DM:150:20	0.664	0.681	0.664	0.663	0.672	0.693	0.672	0.671	0.506	0.596	0.506	0.502
	DM:200:5	0.730	0.746	0.730	0.732	0.742	0.763	0.742	0.744	0.587	0.634	0.587	0.579
	DM:200:10	0.714	0.734	0.714	0.716	0.728	0.753	0.728	0.731	0.559	0.616	0.559	0.553
	DM:200:15	0.688	0.705	0.688	0.688	0.703	0.723	0.703	0.703	0.517	0.591	0.517	0.510
	DM:200:20	0.663	0.682	0.663	0.662	0.676	0.698	0.676	0.676	0.510	0.598	0.510	0.502
	DBOW:100:5	0.800	0.808	0.800	0.800	0.807	0.813	0.807	0.806	0.713	0.721	0.713	0.712
	DBOW:100:10	0.799	0.807	0.799	0.800	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.808	0.699	0.706	0.699	0.697
	DBOW:100:15	0.801	0.807	0.801	0.801	0.811	0.817	0.811	0.811	0.724	0.729	0.724	0.723
	DBOW:100:20	0.801	0.808	0.801	0.801	0.809	0.817	0.809	0.810	0.713	0.720	0.713	0.711
	DBOW:150:5	0.810	0.818	0.810	0.810	0.820	0.828	0.820	0.820	0.726	0.732	0.726	0.725
	DBOW:150:10	0.802	0.808	0.802	0.802	0.814	0.821	0.814	0.815	0.735	0.740	0.735	0.734
	DBOW:150:15	0.799	0.805	0.799	0.799	0.812	0.818	0.812	0.812	0.720	0.725	0.720	0.718
DBOW:150:20	0.812	0.817	0.812	0.812	0.820	0.827	0.820	0.821	0.725	0.730	0.725	0.724	
DBOW:200:5	0.804	0.812	0.804	0.804	0.815	0.823	0.815	0.815	0.728	0.733	0.728	0.727	
DBOW:200:10	0.806	0.813	0.806	0.806	0.817	0.824	0.817	0.817	0.735	0.744	0.735	0.734	
DBOW:200:15	0.806	0.812	0.806	0.806	0.816	0.823	0.816	0.816	0.731	0.737	0.731	0.731	
DBOW:200:20	0.808	0.815	0.808	0.808	0.817	0.824	0.817	0.817	0.742	0.747	0.742	0.741	

MOLECULAR MECHANISM													
Domain	Parameter Setting	Logistic Regression				Support Vector Machine				Bernoulli Naïve Bayes			
		Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁	Acc	Prec	Rec	F ₁
DX	Sum	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.944</u>	<u>0.944</u>	<u>0.944</u>	<u>0.944</u>	<u>0.930</u>	0.935	<u>0.930</u>	0.932
	Average	<u>0.993</u>	<u>0.993</u>	<u>0.993</u>	<u>0.993</u>	0.935	0.936	0.935	<u>0.934</u>	<u>0.949</u>	0.948	<u>0.949</u>	0.948
RX	Sum	<u>0.986</u>	<u>0.986</u>	<u>0.986</u>	<u>0.986</u>	<u>0.856</u>	<u>0.856</u>	<u>0.856</u>	<u>0.855</u>	<u>0.864</u>	<u>0.879</u>	<u>0.864</u>	0.867
	Average	<u>0.988</u>	<u>0.988</u>	<u>0.988</u>	<u>0.988</u>	0.852	<u>0.851</u>	0.852	<u>0.851</u>	<u>0.879</u>	0.878	<u>0.879</u>	0.878
Lab	Sum	<u>0.972</u>	<u>0.972</u>	<u>0.972</u>	<u>0.972</u>	0.884	<u>0.886</u>	0.884	0.884	<u>0.872</u>	<u>0.880</u>	<u>0.872</u>	0.874
	Average	0.966	0.966	0.966	<u>0.965</u>	0.857	0.854	0.857	<u>0.852</u>	0.869	0.866	0.869	<u>0.864</u>
All	Sum	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.991</u>	<u>0.949</u>	<u>0.949</u>	<u>0.949</u>	<u>0.949</u>	0.928	<u>0.931</u>	0.928	<u>0.928</u>
	Average	<u>0.933</u>	0.935	<u>0.933</u>	<u>0.933</u>	<u>0.953</u>	<u>0.953</u>	<u>0.953</u>	<u>0.953</u>	<u>0.813</u>	0.868	<u>0.813</u>	0.824

Acronyms - Acc: Accuracy; DX: Diagnoses or Conditions; F₁: F₁ score; Lab: Measurements; OMOP: Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership; Prec: Precision; Rec: Recall; RX: Medications or Drug Exposures.

Note One. The DM representation is shorthand for the Doc2Vec PV-DM model, which is equivalent to the word2vec CBOW model. The Doc2Vec DBOW representation is shorthand for the PV-DBOW model, which is equivalent to the word2vec skip-gram model. The numbers that appear next to each model indicate the dimensions (i.e., 100, 150, and 200) and the sliding window size (i.e., 5, 10, 15, and 20). The molecular mechanism embeddings were built from a PheKnowLator knowledge graph (v1.0) using a Walking-RDF-and-OWL (modified DeepWalk) with 512 dimensions, 100 walks, a walk length of 20, and a sliding window of 10.

Note Two. The combination of bolding and highlighting is meant to aid in helping interpret the model performance. Bolding (without highlighting or underlying) is used to indicate the best or worst performance metric (i.e., accuracy, precision, recall, or F₁ score) within a clinical domain. Highlighting (without bolding or underlying) is used to indicate the best scoring representation within a given domain across classifiers and performance metrics. Underlying (without bolding or highlighting) is used to indicate the best scoring classifier across all representations and performance metrics. Bolding and highlighting is used to indicate the best (green) or worst (red) score across performance metrics, classifiers, and representations.

Supplemental Table 2. Cleaned and Aligned GEO Sickle Cell Patient Clinical Data (GSE35007).

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860455	2.8	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860210	5.8	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860454	2.8	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0005518)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860402	4.1	M	0.429	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0005518)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860267	4.7	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0005518)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860251	6.6	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0005518)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860226	2.5	F	0.319	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860281	1.4	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860374	1.7	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860265	2.1	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860259	2.4	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860294	2.6	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860404	2.8	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860264	3.1	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860213	3.2	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860420	3.2	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860319	3.4	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860321	3.4	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860368	3.5	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860275	3.6	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860207	5.8	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860304	5.8	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860220	6	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860363	6	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860223	6.1	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860280	6.3	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860282	6.3	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860227	6.6	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860452	6.9	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860446	7.6	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860366	2.5	M	0.303	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860386	1.9	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860418	2.2	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860241	3	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860255	3.2	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860291	3.4	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860300	3.5	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860416	4.7	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860250	7.2	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860249	8.2	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860381	1.7	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukocytosis (HP:0001974)
GSM860440	2.6	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860361	3.7	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)
GSM860441	1.9	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)
GSM860346	1.4	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)
GSM860316	1.3	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)
GSM860412	3.1	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Leukopenia (HP:0001882)
GSM860256	1	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860357	2	M	0.281	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860382	2.8	M	0.281	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860308	3.3	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860438	3.7	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860378	5.1	F	0.308	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860311	4.9	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860336	6.7	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860406	3.7	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860236	5.5	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860252	5.7	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860312	5.7	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860403	5.9	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860301	6.6	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860293	7.7	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860351	9.5	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860306	8.7	F	0.355	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Increased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0005518)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860225	3.7	M	0.317	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860411	0.3	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860405	0.7	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860283	1	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860394	1.4	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860289	1.9	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860297	2	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860270	2.4	M	0.326	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860263	2.7	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860415	2.8	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860266	2.9	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860422	2.9	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860342	3	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860443	3	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860273	3.1	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860318	3.1	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860401	3.1	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860339	3.4	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860352	3.6	M	0.326	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860376	3.8	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860317	4	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860333	4	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860261	4.3	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860354	4.3	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860244	4.5	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860409	4.5	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860433	4.6	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860232	4.7	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860258	4.7	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860295	4.8	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860221	4.9	M	0.302	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860330	4.9	F	0.404	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860419	5	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860327	5.4	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860337	5.4	M	0.302	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860215	5.5	M	0.326	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860222	5.5	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860413	6	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860310	6.1	M	0.401	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860332	6.1	M	0.326	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860453	6.1	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860431	6.2	M	0.302	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860209	6.6	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860325	6.7	M	0.326	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860228	7	F	0.329	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Abnormal Erythrocyte Morphology (HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860262	1.1	M	0.303	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860274	1.6	M	0.281	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860359	2	M	0.303	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860362	2.1	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860365	2.4	M	0.303	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860442	3.2	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860243	3.4	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860439	3.6	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860322	3.9	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860448	4	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860407	4.2	F	0.283	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860276	4.5	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860347	4.5	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860410	4.6	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860235	4.7	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860326	5.6	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860329	5.6	M	0.303	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860340	5.7	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860216	5.9	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860299	5.9	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860349	5.9	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860260	6.2	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860237	6.6	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860287	6.6	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860233	6.7	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860370	6.7	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860231	6.8	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860343	6.9	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860444	1.7	F	0.313	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860217	1.9	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860242	3.7	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860436	3.8	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860248	4.8	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860375	5.2	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860426	7	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860229	7.1	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860314	7.5	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860238	8.7	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860392	1.6	M	0.281	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860364	2.5	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860257	3.6	F	0.305	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860399	4.4	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860323	4.5	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860355	4.8	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860214	5	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860398	0.2	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

GEO ID	Age	Sex	Severity	Group	DOID Concept	HP MCV	HP RBC	HP WBC
GSM860393	1.4	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860371	3.4	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860303	3.5	M	0.31	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860369	3.5	M	0.302	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860239	3.8	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860408	3.8	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860219	4.3	F	0.313	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860424	4.6	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860434	4.6	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860211	5.4	F	0.305	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860396	5.5	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860245	5.8	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860456	7.9	F	0.277	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860288	4.9	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860234	5.2	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860348	5.2	F	0.185	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860414	5.2	M	0.183	HbSC	Hemoglobin C Disease (DOID:2859)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860445	1.7	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860432	1.6	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860298	2.3	F	0.313	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860277	2.9	M	0.378	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860313	3.2	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Normal (NOT HP:0025065)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860279	1.9	M	0.274	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860380	2.3	F	0.313	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860417	2.4	F	0.313	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860388	3.3	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)
GSM860305	3.6	F	0.381	HbSS	Sickle Cell Anemia (DOID:10923)	Decreased Mean Corpuscular Volume (HP:0025066)	Normal (NOT HP:0001877)	Normal (NOT HP:0011893)

Acronym - DOID: Human Disease Ontology; HP: Human Phenotype Ontology; MCV: Mean Corpuscular Volume; RBC: Red Blood Cell Count; WBC: White Blood Cell Count.
Age is measured in years.